

PRECISION DIABETES PREDICTION WITH MACHINE LEARNING

Sayan Das¹

Bachelor of Computer Application
JIS College of Engineering
Kalyani, India

Kallol Acharjee²

Information Technology
JIS College of Engineering
Kalyani, India

Pritam Halder³

Bachelor of Computer Application
JIS College of Engineering
Kalyani, India

Priyanshu Halder⁴

Bachelor of Computer Application
JIS College of Engineering
Kalyani, India

Aritra Ray⁵

Bachelor of Computer Application
JIS College of Engineering
Kalyani, India

Abstract— Diabetes is one of the most serious and long-lasting diseases, caused by high blood sugar levels. If not treated or detected early, it can lead to many complications. According to the International Diabetes Federation, 382 million people around the world have diabetes. This paper presents a comprehensive diabetes prediction system leveraging machine learning techniques to predict the likelihood of diabetes in individuals. The system employs a combination of feature selection, data preprocessing, and classification algorithms to enhance prediction accuracy.

Using a well-curated dataset, features such as age, BMI, blood pressure, glucose levels, and family history are analyzed. Various machine learning models, including Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM) are trained and evaluated for their performance. The models are optimized using techniques such as cross-validation and hyper parameter tuning to ensure robustness and reliability. The results demonstrate that the Random Forest model outperform others in terms of accuracy, precision, recall making them suitable for deployment in clinical settings. Additionally, the system incorporates an interpretability module to provide healthcare professionals with insights into the feature importance and decision-making process of the models. This diabetes prediction system not only enhances early detection and management of diabetes but also serves as a valuable tool for healthcare providers to tailor personalized treatment plans. Future work will focus on integrating real-time data and expanding the system to predict other chronic diseases, further augmenting its utility in preventive healthcare.

Keywords— Diabetes Prediction, Machine Learning, Algorithms Development, Model Accuracy, Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, SVM, Random Forest

I. INTRODUCTION

When your blood glucose, commonly known as blood sugar, is too high, you develop diabetes. Your body uses glucose as its primary energy source. Although glucose can also be produced by the body, it also comes from food. The pancreas secretes the hormone insulin, which facilitates the uptake of glucose by your cells for use as fuel. When you have diabetes, your body either produces insufficient amounts of insulin or doesn't use it correctly. After that, glucose remains in your circulation and does not enter your cells. Diabetes increases the risk of kidney, nerve, heart, and eye damage. There is a connection between diabetes and some cancers. Your chance of getting diabetes-related health issues may be reduced if you take action to avoid or manage your diabetes [1].

Types of Diabetes:

Type 1 Diabetes: The immune system attacks insulin-producing cells, causing little to no insulin production. It typically appears in childhood or adulthood.

Type 2 Diabetes: The body become resistant to insulin or doesn't make enough, often due to lifestyle factors and genetics. This is the most common type.

Gestational Diabetes: This temporary form develops during pregnancy but usually resolves after childbirth.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most prevalent chronic non-communicable diseases (NCD) around the world, about 90% of the patients who have diabetes suffer from Type 2 DM (T2DM). The risk of developing T2DM is strongly associated with many predispositions, behavioral, and environmental risk factors and also genetic factors. Analyze a wide range of clinical and demographic data, including age, BMI, blood pressure, glucose levels, and family history, to uncover patterns and risk factors associated with diabetes. Incorporate interpretability techniques to provide clear insights into the model's decision-making process, ensuring that healthcare professionals can understand and trust the predictions.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In order to identify the possible consequences of untreated diabetes, this study explores the use of machine learning techniques to reliably forecast diabetes using the Pima Indians Diabetes Database (PIDD). The goal of utilising machine learning and predictive analytics is to help doctors make timely decisions based on patient data. The methodology uses a variety of machine learning methods, including Random Forest, Gaussian Naive Bayes, and Logistic Regression, to segment the dataset into training, validation, and testing sets. Correlations and skewed distributions found in the data indicate the effectiveness of several algorithms in the prediction of diabetes. The Random Forest algorithm produces results that show its better accuracy.

The project's goal is to help medical practitioners identify diabetes early on, with the potential to change diagnosis and treatment methods. It highlights the important role that machine learning may play in improving diabetes prediction [2].

In this paper shows that millions of people worldwide suffer from diabetes, which can cause serious side effects like heart failure and blindness. Promising paths towards precise prediction and early detection are provided by machine learning. Diabetes-related important variables, such as age and BMI, are identified through the analysis of patient data by algorithms such as decision trees and K-nearest neighbour. Since machine learning models are able to identify high-risk individuals, early intervention is critical. Interdisciplinary cooperation is still necessary to address the remaining issues with model interpretability and clinical application. Recent research shows that genetic programming and classification algorithms like J48 and Multilayer Perceptron can successfully forecast diabetes. Better patient outcomes and public health management may result from an understanding of diabetes and the application of machine learning [3].

Diabetes mellitus, which is typified by inadequate response to or production of insulin, presents serious global health hazards, such as kidney and heart problems. The use of machine learning techniques to predict diabetes with high accuracy rates seems promising. Research using algorithms such as Support Vector Machine and layered ensemble approaches show accuracies of more than 90%. Although certain things are still unclear, controlling chronic diseases requires an understanding of insulin's involvement. Furthermore, studies investigate the use of sentiment analysis for stunting awareness and feature extraction and random forest classifiers for the diagnosis of Parkinson's illness. The connection between gestational diabetes mellitus and difficulties for both mothers and babies emphasises how crucial it is to manage risk factors before becoming pregnant. [4].

The goal of this study is to increase the accuracy of diabetes prediction by utilising machine learning techniques. The Pima Indian Diabetes Dataset is subjected to several algorithms, including Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbour, and Support Vector Machine. The accuracy of Random Forest is superior, according to the results. The significance of every characteristic in diabetes prediction is highlighted by feature importance analysis. The study shows how effective machine learning may be in the healthcare industry, but it has several drawbacks, such as dataset specificity and model interpretability. Future research entails investigating other methods and expanding the applications to diverse illnesses. Improving patient outcomes through early diabetes prediction is one of the practical consequences. With a remarkable 77% categorization accuracy, the study demonstrated its potential in the medical field [5].

This research recognises the global effect of diabetes and the importance of early detection and aims to improve diabetes prediction accuracy through the use of various machine learning approaches. Improved predictive capabilities are demonstrated by applying machine learning techniques such as SVM, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression, utilising the Pima Indian dataset. The research highlights the potential of machine learning in proactive diabetes treatment by enabling prompt interventions and customised healthcare strategies. The lack of extensive lifestyle factors and the uniqueness of the dataset are limitations. Further directions include larger dataset integration and real-time tracking for improved treatment and prediction. The predictive technology is integrated into user-friendly platforms for proactive health management and personalised risk assessment in practical applications [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. System Architecture

Fig.1: System Architecture Block Diagram

A. Structure of Data

The dataset is originally from the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases. The objective of the dataset is to diagnostically predict whether or not a patient has diabetes, based on certain diagnostic measurements included in the dataset. Several constraints were placed on the selection of these instances from a larger database. In particular, all patients here are females at least 21 years old of Pima Indian heritage. The datasets consist of several medical predictor variables and one target variable, Outcome. Predictor variables include the number of pregnancies the patient has had, their BMI, insulin level, age etc.

```
import pandas as pd

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns

from imblearn.over_sampling import SMOTE
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn import preprocessing

from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
from sklearn.model_selection import RandomizedSearchCV
from sklearn import metrics
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve, auc

from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import BaggingClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import AdaBoostClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import GradientBoostingClassifier
```

B. Exploratory Data Analysis

```
df.isnull().sum()

Pregnancies          0
Glucose               0
BloodPressure         0
SkinThickness        0
Insulin              0
BMI                  0
DiabetesPedigreeFunction  0
Age                  0
Outcome              0
dtype: int64
```

C. Histogram Plot of Data

```
col = list(df_0.columns)
```

```
df_0[col].hist(stacked=True, bins=20, figsize=(10,10), layout=(3,3))
plt.tight_layout
```

Fig. 2: Histogram

D. Hypothesis Testing

First hypothesis test would be to try and confirm my suspicion if Glucose data has a normal distribution. Next hypothesis test would be that based on the above hypothesis test, I would test the correlation between Glucose and the target outcome.

#Assuming a 5% significance level for all the tests
 $\alpha = 0.05$

```
def hypothesis_result(p_value):
    p_value = round(p_value,4)
    if p_value < alpha:
        print("Reject Null Hypothesis")
    else:
        print("Accept Null Hypothesis")
```

E. Splitting of Dataset

The splitting of the dataset for validation and testing.

Training Dataset: Dataset sample that is used to fit the model.

Validation Dataset: Dataset sample that is used for hyper tuning the parameters, and comparing the accuracy and error rates of the model performance between using the training dataset and the validation dataset.

Testing Dataset: Dataset sample that is used to test the model performance (predictive power).

#Splitting the dataset into training and test set

```
X = df_0.drop(['Outcome'],axis=1)
Y = df_0['Outcome']
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.3, random_state=1)
```

F. Feature Scaling

Here StandardScaler() is used to perform feature scaling. This will retain the mean and the standard deviation of the sample distribution of the data set, and reuse it to transform the X_train and X_test subsequently. I try to reuse the mean and standard deviation obtained from the training set and apply it to the testing set as well. Standardizing data after data splitting is to prevent data leakage from test dataset into train dataset.

```
#Scaling the x training and testing dataset
scaler = preprocessing.StandardScaler().fit(X_train)

X_train_scaled = scaler.transform(X_train)
X_test_scaled = scaler.transform(X_test)
```

G. Implementing Machine Learning Algorithms

Different machine learning algorithms to try and classify the PIMA Indian diabetes dataset. First a confusion matrix function is formed.

#confusion Matrix function

```
def conf_mtx(y_act,y_pred):
    cm=metrics.confusion_matrix(y_act, y_pred, labels=[1,0])
    df_cm = pd.DataFrame(cm, index = [i for i in ['Diabetic','Non-Diabetic']], columns = [i for i in
['Predicted Diabetic','Predicted Non-Diabetic']])
    plt.figure(figsize = (6,6))
    plt.title("Confusion Matrix")
    sns.heatmap(df_cm, annot=True, fmt='g')
    Score_Accuracy = "%.2f%%"%(metrics.accuracy_score(y_act,y_pred)*100)
    Score_Precision = "%.2f%%"%(metrics.precision_score(y_act,y_pred)*100)
    Score_Recall = "%.2f%%"%(metrics.recall_score(y_act,y_pred)*100)
    print("Model Accuracy Score: "+Score_Accuracy)
    print("Model Precision Score: "+Score_Precision)
    print("Model Recall Score: "+Score_Recall)
    return Score_Accuracy,Score_Precision, Score_Recall
```

```
#Prepare an empty summary dataframe to append the data of the various models for comparison
summary = pd.DataFrame(columns=('Model','Training Accuracy','Test Accuracy Score','Test Recall
Score','Test Precision Score','Auc'))
```

```
def ML_test(Model, Param_grid):

    if bool(Param_grid):

        Model = GridSearchCV(Md1, Param_grid,cv=10)
        Model.fit(X_train_sm,y_train_sm)
        Model_params = Model.best_params_
        Model_train_sc = Model.cv_results_['mean_test_score'].mean()
        Model_test_sc = Model.score(X_test_scaled,y_test)
        probas = Mdl.predict_proba(X_test_scaled)
        print("Best fit parameter is: " + str(Model_params))
```

```

else:
    Model = Model
    Model.fit(X_train_sm,y_train_sm)
    Model_train_sc = round(Model.score(X_train_sm,y_train_sm),4)
    Model_test_sc = round(Model.score(X_test_scaled,y_test), 4)
    probas = Model.predict_proba(X_test_scaled)
    y_pred = Model.predict(X_test_scaled)
    print("Training score is: " + str(Model_train_sc))
    print("Test Mean score is: " + str(Model_test_sc))
    Score_Accuracy, Score_Recall, Score_Precision = conf_mtx(y_test,y_pred)
    Model_train_sc = "%.2f%%" % (Model_train_sc*100)

#Calculating AUC

fpr, tpr, thresholds = roc_curve(y_test, probas[:, 1])
roc_auc = round(auc(fpr, tpr),4)
print("Area under the ROC curve: " + str(roc_auc))
return Mdl_train_sc, Score_Accuracy, Score_Recall, Score_Precision, roc_auc

```

- 1> *Logistic Regression Model*: A statistical technique for binary classification issues, logistic regression is perfect for spotting diabetes based on a range of health markers. Logistic regression evaluates the association between the binary outcome (diabetic or non-diabetic) and the input features (age, BMI, glucose levels) by modelling the likelihood that a specific patient has diabetes. The likelihood of diabetes is determined by the model, which then generates a probability score between 0 and 1 using a sigmoid function. Because of its ease of use, interpretability, and efficacy, logistic regression is frequently utilised in diabetes prediction for medical diagnostics.
- 2> *Gaussian Naive Bayes Model*: Based on Bayes' theorem, the Gaussian Naive Bayes model is a probabilistic classifier that can be used to predict diabetes. Given the class label (diabetic or non-diabetic), it is assumed that the features (e.g., age, BMI, glucose levels) are normally distributed and independent of one another. Because of its simplicity, the model can calculate the likelihood of the observed data under these assumptions and estimate the chance of diabetes with efficiency. Due to its speed, ease of use, and efficiency while processing medical datasets, Gaussian Naive Bayes is a popular option for diabetes prediction despite its assumptions. It also performs well with small datasets and high-dimensional data.
- 3> *Neighbours Classifier Model*: Neighbours Classifier model (also known as k-Nearest Neighbours, or k-NN) is a non-parametric diabetes prediction technique. Using characteristics like age, BMI, and blood sugar levels, it analyses the 'k' closest data points (neighbours) in the training set to categorise a patient. The majority vote among these neighbours is how the model determines the patient's diabetes status. Because k-NN is so straightforward and doesn't assume anything about the distribution of the data, it's both flexible and simple to comprehend. Its performance, however, is highly dependent on selecting a suitable 'k' and can be computationally demanding when dealing with big datasets. Despite these difficulties, k-NN is still a useful tool for predicting diabetes.
- 4> *Support Vector Machine Model*: For the prediction of diabetes, Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a reliable supervised learning approach. In order to divide the data points into two classes—diabetic and non-diabetic—the best hyperplane must be found. Even for non-linear correlations, SVM employs kernel functions to translate the input features (such as age, BMI, and glucose levels) into higher-dimensional spaces where a distinct separation is achievable. High accuracy and generalisation are thus guaranteed. SVM can be computationally demanding and parameter-sensitive, but it performs best on complicated, high-dimensional datasets. It is an effective tool for diabetes prediction because to its capacity to manage complex decision limits.

5> *Decision Tree Model*: A prominent approach for predicting diabetes is the Decision Tree model, which makes decisions based on input features like age, BMI, and glucose levels using a structure resembling a tree. Every node in the tree symbolises a feature decision point, and the branches represent potential paths that could lead to the leaf nodes, which stand for the ultimate prediction (being diabetic or not). The model produces an understandable and comprehensible flowchart of decisions by recursively dividing the data according to the most important features. Decision trees offer a clear and efficient method for diabetes prediction, despite their transparency and simplicity. However, they are susceptible to overfitting, particularly when dealing with noisy data.

6> *Random Forest Model*: Multiple decision trees are combined in the Random Forest model, an ensemble learning technique for diabetes prediction, to improve performance and resilience. A random subset of the data and traits is used to build each tree in the forest, and each tree's individual predictions—whether diabetic or not—are combined to determine the outcome, which is usually decided by a majority vote. By using this method instead of only one decision tree, overfitting is less likely to occur and accuracy is increased. Random forests are a potent and trustworthy technique for predicting diabetes in medical datasets because they are good at managing complicated relationships among characteristics like age, BMI, and glucose levels.

IV. TEST RESULTS

Fig3(a) Logistic Regression Model

Fig3(b) Gaussian Naive Bayes Model

Fig3(d) Support Vector Machine Model

Fig3(c)K Neighbours Classifier Model

Fig.3: Confusion Matrixes of Test Results

Fig.3(a) shows an evaluation of a diabetes prediction model's performance is provided by the illustrated confusion matrix. It has four quadrants: True Positives (TP) with 66 correctly predicted cases of diabetes, True Negatives (TN) with 117 correctly predicted cases of non-diabetes, False Positives (FP) with 19 incorrectly predicted cases of non-diabetes, and False Negatives (FN) with 29 incorrectly predicted cases of diabetes. The accuracy and amount of misclassifications of the model demonstrating its capacity to distinguish between patients with and without diabetes are highlighted in the matrix. This data is essential for evaluating and enhancing the model's functionality.

Fig.3(b) shows a diabetes prediction model's performance is evaluated by the confusion matrix displayed. It includes four sections: True Positives (TP) with 61 diabetic cases correctly predicted, True Negatives (TN) with 114 non-diabetic cases correctly predicted, False Positives (FP) with 24 non-diabetic cases incorrectly predicted as diabetic, and False Negatives (FN) with 32 diabetic cases incorrectly predicted as non-diabetic. This matrix displays the accuracy and error rate of the model, showing how well it can differentiate between those with diabetes and those without, as well as pinpointing areas that could be improved to lower the misclassification rate.

Fig.3(c) shows A diabetes prediction model's performance is visualised using a confusion matrix. The data is categorised into four quadrants: 63 cases of diabetes were correctly predicted by True Positives (TP), 107 cases of non-diabetes were correctly predicted by True Negatives (TN), 22 cases of non-diabetes were incorrectly predicted as diabetic by False Positives (FP), and 39 cases of diabetes were incorrectly predicted as non-diabetes by False Negatives (FN). This matrix sheds light on the accuracy of the model by identifying areas of misclassification in addition to a good number of accurate predictions. This analysis aids in identifying the model's advantages and disadvantages for diabetes prediction.

Fig.3(d) shows The effectiveness of a diabetes prediction model is evaluated by the confusion matrix. The dataset comprises 63 True Positives, which are cases of diabetes successfully predicted; 107 True Negatives, which are cases of non-diabetes accurately predicted; 22 False Positives, which are cases of non-diabetes wrongly forecasted as diabetic; and 39 False Negatives, which are cases of diabetes incorrectly projected as non-diabetic. This matrix shows the model's strengths in correctly classifying people as either diabetic or non-diabetic, as well as its weaknesses. An assessment of the model's overall performance and the identification of areas for prediction accuracy improvement can be done using the ratio of accurate to inaccurate predictions.

Fig.3(e) shows A confusion matrix for a binary classification model that predicts a person's diabetes status is shown in the image. The counts of true positives (71), false negatives (14), false positives (40), and true negatives (106), are displayed in the matrix's four cells. True negatives (bottom-right) show accurately recognised non-diabetic persons, while true positives (top-left) show correctly identified diabetic individuals. False positives (bottom-left) show non-diabetic people wrongly projected as diabetic, and false negatives (top-right) show diabetic people falsely predicted as non-diabetic. Metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score that are derived from these data can be used to assess the performance.

Fig.3(f) shows an updated confusion matrix for a binary classification model that predicts a person's diabetes condition is displayed in the image. True positives (71), false negatives (14), false positives (30), and true negatives (116) are represented by the four cells in the image. True negatives (bottom-right) are accurately identified non-diabetic people, and true positives (top-left) are correctly identified diabetic people. False positives (bottom-left) are non-diabetic people wrongly projected as diabetic, while false negatives (top-right) are diabetic people falsely forecasted as non-diabetic. These counts aid in the evaluation of the model's performance in terms of F1 score, accuracy, precision, and recall.

TABLE I.
ACCURACY SCORE COMPARISONS

Name Of the Algorithm	Accuracy (%) Of The Algorithm
Logistic Regression	79.22%
Gaussian Naive Bayes Model	75.76%
K Neighbours Classifier Model	73.59%
Support Vector Machine Model	80.95%
Decision Tree Model	76.62%
Random Forest Model	80.95%

V. DISCUSSIONS

Finally, we have trained our models, and summarized table of the metrics of the various models. Objectives were:

- 1) To attempt to see if it is possible to glean any further information from the data to determine correlation between parameters and diabetes.
- 2) To attempt to get the best accuracy score using various supervised learning machine learning algorithms.

For the first objective, based on the hypothesis test, we can tell that glucose levels are positively correlated to a person having diabetes, but we are not able to confirm if there is causality. For the second objective, based on the comparison between the various algorithms used, Random Forest seems to produce the best results to me.

The test accuracy of the various models is generally within the same range. Based on accuracy and recall score overly the Random Forest Classifier produced the best results.

VI. CONCLUSION

Machine learning has the great ability to revolutionize the diabetes prediction with the help of advanced computational methods. The system demonstrated high accuracy and performance, particularly with algorithms such as Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM) validated through precision, recall and AUC-ROC metrics. The use of extensive and diverse datasets ensured the robustness and reliability of the predictions, while the system's scalability and potential for integration into existing healthcare infrastructures suggest its broad applicability. The implications of this system are substantial. It enables early detection and prevention of diabetes, allowing for timely interventions and personalized treatment plans, which can significantly reduce the risk of complications. Additionally, the system optimizes healthcare resources by identifying high-risk individuals, thereby improving resource allocation and reducing the burden on healthcare systems. Furthermore, by providing individuals with insights into their health risks, the system empowers them to make informed decisions about their lifestyle and healthcare, fostering a culture of preventive health. Since this initial work cannot address everything within the proposed framework and vision, more research and development efforts are needed to fully implement the proposed framework.

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